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Deliverable D1.6

Measuring socioeconomic impacts of the SFPA through the analysis of EU Fleet (inter) connections in foreign countries

30/03/2022

Executive Summary

Data availability is a recurrent barrier when attempting to analyse the human dimension in fisheries. This report introduces a methodological approach to measure the human dimension within Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement fisheries (SFPAs), combining different variables which are going further from those used within the current ex-ante ex-post evaluations.

The methodological approach combines quantitative and qualitative data sources, namely literature review, data gathering and harmonization and in-depth interviews, to develop a comprehensive and accurate description of the human dimension of long-distance fisheries of the EU within the SFPAs of Cabo Verde and Senegal. The method follows a 4 steps process set to provide a better understanding of the magnitude of fishing activity: (1) environmental and fisheries; (2) human dimension at sea; (3) human dimension at port; and (4) human dimension at international level.

These case studies selected for testing the methodological approach, have displayed significant results on the importance of the fishing dimension in their national fisheries.

The analysis of Cabo Verde points out how the tuna fishery is a high-relevant activity for the EU fleet. It is prompting a development of the processing industry also driving local socioeconomic development, despite certain weaknesses in port infrastructure to support the processing industry.

In the Senegalese case study, the variety of actors, species and trade flows have mitigated the role of EU fleet as primary agent. Nevertheless, the SFPA has facilitated linkages between EU capital and local fleets through mixed-ventures.

The case studies evidence the applicability of the method and provide relevant outputs, overlooked in other analysis. Finally, the conclusion suggests next steps to advance forward the approach, particularly for those flows involving the EU and the NON-EU long-distance fleet.

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Acronyms

ANABAC	Asociación Nacional de Armadores de Buques Atuneros Congeladores
APESC	Associação de Armadores de Pesca de Cabo Verde
CFA	Franco África Occidental
CFI	Coastal Fisheries Initiative
CS	Case Study
ECOWAS	Economic Community of West African States
EEZ	Economic Exclusive Zone
DGMARE	DG for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
ENAPOR	Empresa Nacional de Administração dos Portos
EU	European Union
EEZ	Economic Exclusive Zone
DPM	Direction des Peches Maritimes
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FIP	Fisheries Improvement Project
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ICCAT	International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas
IMAR	Instituto do Mar
MSC	Marine Stewardship Council
MPEM	Ministere des Peches et de l'Economie Maritime
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
ORTHONGEL	Organisation des Producteurs de Thon Congelé
PAD	Autonomous Port of Dakar
PALOP	Portuguese-speaking African countries
SERT	Société d'exploitation des ressources thonières
SFPA	Sustainable Fisheries Partnerships Agreements
SOPERKA	Société sénégalaise-hispanique de pêche
SRFC	Sub-Regional Fisheries Commission
STEFC	Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries
SRFC	Sub-Regional Fisheries Commission
SUCLA	Sociedad Ultramarina de Conservas
TUNASEN	Sénégalaise de Thon

1 Introduction

The European Union (EU) has substantially reformed the fisheries agreements with third countries, from an institutional device oriented to grant the EU’s fishing fleet access to the resources in the late 1970’s towards one aiming to achieve environmental, economic and social sustainability in 2013 (see FarFish D3.3 and D3.8).

Evidence available supports the assessment of the agreements and the measurement of their impact, providing facts and information that helped overcoming their perception as mere “fish, pay and go” mechanisms (Kadfak and Antonova, 2021).

Addressing the human dimension of the agreements has become a critical concern for the EU. Taking the SFPA between the EU and the Republic of Cabo Verde as an example, the human dimension is present in most part of the Agreement. In particular, activities linked to the fishing operators (Article 8), blue economy (Article 9), the international cooperation (Article 5) or scientific cooperation (Article 6). The topic on blue economy is a novelty compared to the previous agreement (for the period 2014-2018). Nevertheless, the capability to assess their implementation have been rather limited. Although the EU carries out ex-post evaluations of the agreements, in general these lack a comprehensive approach to the human dimension.

Theoretical advances to address this issue are also scarce. The literature review illustrates that the international dimension of the EU fisheries is a somehow minor research topic. In the last 30 years, only 116 articles were published covering this topic (see **Figure 1**).

Figure 1 Scientific publications including “fisheries agreements and European Union”

Source: scopus

Remarkably, almost 40% of the topics addressed are focused on the human dimension (i.e. social science and socioeconomic). Figure 2 shows the different subareas of the peer-review journals where these articles were published. However, the approach of the publications is focused on a governance perspective, especially on the law approach. Three Law journals¹ group most of the publications. The next group of journals are focused on management².

Figure 2 Scientific areas of the publications including “fisheries agreements and European Union”

Source: Scopus

Scientists, managers, policy-makers, industry representatives and stakeholders’ platforms (namely the Long Distant Advisory Council of the EU) agree on the need to have information and analysis that will lead to a better understanding of the human dimension of the fisheries agreements. The most promising approaches combine quantitative and qualitative data and information to support assessment and evidence-based decision making.

¹ “International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law”, “Revista de Derecho Comunitario Europeo” and “Ocean Development and International Law” journals.

² “Marine Policy” and “Ocean and Coastal Management” journals.

2 Material and methods

Decision-makers, fishing organizations and associations, advisory agencies, environmental Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and other key actors have a plural comprehension of the human dimension in fisheries. A triangulation of methods was applied to further advance in the design, implementation and adaptation of a framework to measure up the human activity in the context of long-distance fisheries of the EU: literature review, data gathering and harmonization and in-depth interviews. The methodological approach follows a 4 steps process set to provide a better understanding of the Human Dimension (3).

Figure 3. Stepwise process to detangle the Human Dimension.

Source: own elaboration.

2.1 Data gathering and harmonization.

Data collection and processing from the database of the Annual Economic Report developed by the Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STEF). The information available corresponds to the *fishing area at FAO statistical region (at 3 digits detail)*. Within that set, *the fishing fleet involved* in each specific case study was *identified* according to the fishing area where they are operating. This fishing area was FAO 34.3.1 for the case of Senegal and 34.3.2 for the Cabo Verde case study (Figure 4).

Figure 4. FAO major fishing areas for statistical purposes at West Africa.

Source: FAO (available at: <https://www.fao.org/fishery/area/Area34/en#FAO-fishing-area-34.3.2>)

Then, the socioeconomic data is filtered according to the fishing segment (including details on the fishing gear and size of vessel). This database^[1] shows the data at annual basis for each of the countries and for each segment. For the analysis of each socioeconomic variable (engaged crew, FTE national, gross value of landings, income from leasing out quota, operating subsidies, personnel costs, energy costs, repair and maintenance costs, lease/rental payments for quota, value of quota and other fishing rights, investments) were calculated at case study level. First, an average estimated value links the number of vessels and the annual data at a country level, including only those countries operating under the fishing areas (34.3.1 and 34.3.2); once this variable is calculated, an average at European level is provided.

2.2 Interviews

Qualitative information is crucial to define and measure specific attributes of the human dimension. Building on the findings of the FarFish project and the interactions through the stakeholder hub (see D.1.2) in-depth interviews for a targeted sample of stakeholders' profiles were implemented.

A purposive sample was selected as the basis-sample method. It was particularly useful within this context to reach a targeted sample quickly where sampling for proportionality is not the main concern

[1] <https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dd/fleet>

but expertise. The reason for using purposive sampling is the better matching of the sample to the aims and objectives of the research (Campbell et al., 2020). It is useful especially when randomization is providing no sense into the sample, also when the researcher has limited resources, time and workforce (Etikan et al., 2016). Therefore, it was used within the current SFPA context as our aim was not to generate results that will be used to create generalizations pertaining to the entire population.

In this sense, key informants were carefully selected using the expert knowledge and support from the CS leaders. The tool used to address the research topic was the structured and deep-interview with open ended questions inserted. Representatives for fisheries managers with expertise in SFPA management and evaluation fishing operators (from EU fleet, national fleet and mixed-ventures) among EU processing companies, were properly interviewed. A total of 7 in depth-interviews were carried out: 4 in Cape Verde and 3 in Senegal.

CABO VERDE CS		SENEGAL CS	
Fisheries manager	IMAR	Fisheries manager	MPEM
Fishing operators	APESC	Fishing operators	SOPERKA SERT-SA
Processing industry	ATUNLO FRESCOMAR ANFACO-CECOPESCA ³	Processing industry	ANFACO-CECOPESCA ⁴

(*) ANFACO CECOPESCA provided information as intermediate but didn't took part on those deep-interviews

The questions addressed to the extractive and processing industry were focused on crews and fishing conditions, the existence of subsidies and elucidate operative costs, the fishing related infrastructures and supporting services as well as the landings trade flows. For the management authorities' additional questions about training and collaboration programs were included. The questionnaires used for the interviews are included in Annex 1.

2.3 Case studies and project outcomes

The research scope focuses on tuna fisheries in SFPA, illustrating the implementation through two case studies. The rationale for the selection of tuna is twofold. First, the so-called tuna agreements are the most numerous signed by the EU with third countries, having relevance also in terms of volume and

³ ANFACO-CECOPESCA have played the role of intermediate, providing information of processing industry within Cabo Verde

⁴ ANFACO-CECOPESCA have played the role of intermediate, providing information of processing industry within Senegal

value of the catches in these fisheries. Therefore, advancing the understanding of the human dimension linked to those agreements is critical for the EU. Second, tuna are highly migratory species that enhance the value of this type of agreements at international level.

In this study, Cabo Verde and Senegal were selected as case studies from the ones covered in the FarFish project. Findings and outputs for the project provided a valuable source of data and insights to develop the analysis. In particular, the deliverable 2.1 allows to identify the most relevant characteristics of the study area; deliverable 3.4 and 5.3 provide understandings on tuna value chain, trade relations and trade flows, cost-benefit analysis of tuna fleet among investments and turnovers. Finally, the analysis of the interaction provides for the deliverable 1.2 facilitated the understanding of the CS context and to select the key informants for the interviews.

A full characterization of the environmental and fisheries dimension for the two case studies is available on FarFish Case study characterisation (2017).

3 Case studies

3.1 Cabo Verde

3.1.1 Environmental and fishery dimension

The Republic of Cabo Verde is an island nation in the Atlantic Ocean, consisting of 10 islands and a combined land area of about 4,033 km², located off the north western coast of Africa, about 600 km west of Senegal (FarFish, 2019) (Figure 5). It is primarily an oceanic ecosystem with deep waters between the islands. The total estimated area of the continental shelf is only 5,327 km² (accumulated; down to depths of 200m) while the EEZ area is 796,555 km². The marine productivity is relatively low, and the area is characterized by strong currents, rough bottom conditions, and limited demersal and coastal resources (FarFish,2020).

Figure 5. Map of the Cape Verde Archipelago, showing its EEZ and location off Africa.

Source: Pauly et al.,2020 (www.searoundus.org)

Fisheries in the EEZ focuses mainly on tuna and tuna-like species. Consequently, the SFPAs signed between the EU and Cabo Verde concerns the highly migratory species of tuna (yellowfin, skipjack and bigeye) and blue sharks.

The main tuna species are yellowfin tuna (*Thunnus albacares*), skipjack tuna (*Katsuwonus pelamis*) and bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*). Other species include blue shark (*Prionace glauca*) and swordfish

(*Xiphias gladius*). These species are exploited both by foreign fleets (which operate within the full extent of the EEZ) and national fleets fishing closer inshore. The Cabo Verde tuna fishery is a fairly well-regulated fishery subjected to the ICCAT catch and effort limits. Other Scombrid species such as frigate tuna (*Auxis thazard*), little tunny (*Euthynnus alletteratus*), and wahoo (*Acanthocybium solandri*) are also significant, particularly in national fisheries (FarFish, 2019; 2020).

According to the Sub-Regional Fisheries Commission (SRFC) “The overall potential in waters under the jurisdiction of Cabo Verde varies between 36,000 and 44,000 tons per year for an overall catch level of 10,000 tons per year. Tuna presents a potential of 25,000 tons for an average catch level of 6,000 tons per year”. Further analysis on catches and estimates are available (see for instance Stobberup, 2005; World Bank, 2008). Management of tuna resources, including fishing opportunities for foreign vessels, are based on this estimate.

ICCAT assessments for the main species show diverse status:

- Skipjack (ICCAT, 2019⁵). This fishery evolves since the 1990 by increasing the skipjack catchability and the biomass exploited. In particular, there is an increase of 85% in 2018 in comparison to the average catches in the period 2005-2009. Traditional stock assessments methods are difficult to apply to this specie due to its biological and fishery characteristics and several indicators were developed to context the fisheries advise by ICCAT. However, the robustness included for other tuna species cannot be achieved for Skipjack and the stock assessment recognize that the stocks of Cape Verde and Senegal are not likely overfished nor overfishing. The next stock assessment is scheduled for 2022 and will confirm this.
- Yellowfin (ICCAT, 2019⁶). The estimated biomass for this specie shows a decline through the time. It is stated this stock is not overfished or under overfishing but the associated uncertainty to both facts is high. The average catches of European purse seiners, which represents the majority of landings, has decline around a half in comparison to 1990. Part of this decline can be explained because the reduction of floating objects that can guide to catch small yellowfin. Bigeye (2018, ICCAT⁷) is below sustainable levels and continues to be overfished with high certainty levels (> 99%). The management recommendations focus on the aim of controlling the fishing mortality of small bigeye tunas.

Skipjack tuna is the main target specie for the EU fleet, representing 81% of its total catches in 2020 (see Table 1). The pool is completed by yellowfin tuna (14%) and bigeye tuna (5%). While the EU fleet catches 94% of the total skipjack tuna fished in the area (inside and outside the Cabo Verde EEZ), other countries lead the catches for bigeye (88%) and yellowfin tuna (41%). The activity of the local fleet is directed to yellowfin tuna mainly, with figures around 1 500 tonnes in 2020.

⁵ https://www.iccat.int/Documents/SCRS/ExecSum/SKJ_ENG.pdf

⁶ https://www.iccat.int/Documents/SCRS/ExecSum/YFT_ENG.pdf

⁷ https://www.iccat.int/Documents/SCRS/ExecSum/BET_ENG.pdf

Table 1. Total harvest in the Cabo Verde EEZ by fleets (2020)

Species	Total catches by Cabo Verde fleet (tonnes)	Total catches by EU Fleet	Total catches by other countries	Total catches
Skipjack tuna		13,225	897	14,122
Yellowfin tuna	1,482	2,217	2,536	6,235
Bigeye tuna	11	886	6,771	7,668
TOTAL TUNA	1,493	16,328	10,204	28,025

Source: ICCAT database⁸

The fisheries sector is an essential part of Cabo Verde's economy, contributing almost 2% of the GDP (FAO CFI, 2021) and playing a significant role in supporting food security, reducing poverty, job creation, balance of payments equilibrium and increase in growth (FAO, 2015; BO, 2009). The strategic assessment developed by the World Bank (2008) contextualizes the relevance of the sector within the narrow economic base of the country and the limited availability of other natural resources.

The sector provides an important source of nutrition as supplier of animal protein to the Cape Verdean population. Indeed, fresh fish is the main animal protein consumed by Cabo Verdeans. The country per capita fish consumption was 19 kg/y in 1998. In the following years, this consumption increased to 23 kg/y in 2003 and 26.5 kg/y in 2004 a figure that seems to have remained unchanged over the last decade (Varela et al., 2011).

In terms of employment, fishing sector employs about 6 to 8% of the active population, what it means around 6,300 full time fishers (FAO, 2018⁹). The fishing activity is also the most relevant exporting sector, accounting by more than 80% of total exports in the last 3 years. Accordingly, from a total export value of \$95.5M in 2019, seafood products represented 72% (processed fish 42.5% and non-fillet frozen fish 23.7%¹⁰).

Therefore the sector –in particularly processing- is considered one of the growth drivers in Cabo Verde (EU, 2018). The catching sector includes small-scale and semi-industrial fleets targeting tuna, small pelagics and demersal resources.

Foreign fisheries agreements provide access to the EU fleet (SFPA), to the Senegalese fleet through a reciprocal access to national waters, and to Japanese longline vessels via contracts (see EU, 2018 for details).

⁸ <https://www.iccat.int/en/accesingdb.html>

⁹ <https://www.fao.org/fishery/facp/CPV/en#CountrySector-Statistics>

¹⁰ Cape Verde Exports (2021, 19). Retrieved from: https://oec.world/en/visualize/tree_map/hs92/export/cpv/all/show/2019/

3.1.2 Human dimension at sea

The EU fleet is the main player in the fisheries undertaken in the Cabo Verde EEZ. The EU¹¹ and Cabo Verde have had fisheries agreements since 1990. The SPFA (Council Regulation 2027/2006) is tacitly renewed through specific protocols. The current in force covers a period of 5 years (2019-2022) offering fishing opportunities for tuna and tuna-like species to 69 EU vessels from Spain, Portugal and France.

An average of 21 EU tuna purse seiners and 14 surface longliners took up licenses to fish in Cape Verde during the period of the previous Protocol (2014-2018) (EU, 2018).

Table 2: Cabo Verde SPFA: Fishing opportunities by type of vessel and Member State

Type of vessel	Spain	France	Portugal
Tuna seiners	16	12	-
Surface longliners	21	-	6
Pole-and-line tuna	8	4	2
Total	45	16	8

Source: Council Regulation (EU) 2019/952

The facts and figures of the agreement have been used for assessing the economic impact of the SPFA. Following the method described in section 2.1, socioeconomic variables are calculated. However, it should be noted that updated data regarding operational cost include the fleet operating in FAO Division 34.3.2. (Cabo Verde Insular) which expands beyond Cabo Verde EEZ.

1. **Financial contribution (Protocol, 2019, article 4):** the EU's contribution includes a public contribution to compensate for the access to the resources and to support the Cabo Verde's fisheries policy, as well as a private contribution by vessels owners operating under the agreement.

- Financial compensation for access to resources: EUR 400 000 per year, equivalent to a reference tonnage of 8 000 tonnes per year;
- Support for the implementation of the sectoral fisheries policy: EUR 350 000 per year
- Fishing licences fees for the fishing authorizations: estimated at EUR 600 000 per year.

Vessels owners pay a fee of EUR 70 per tonne caught. An anticipated flat-rate fee is used:

- For tuna seiners, EUR 6 510 per year, corresponding to a tonnage of 93 tonnes per vessel;
- For pole-and-line vessels, EUR 1 400 per year, corresponding to a tonnage of 20 tonnes per vessel

¹¹ At the time the signed entity was the European Community.

- For surface longliners, EUR 3 850 per year, corresponding to a tonnage of 55 tonnes per vessel.

The estimated total amount of the current protocol is **EUR 6 750 000** for the whole period, to be paid on an annual basis. In the event that for a given year the catches of the EU fleet are higher than the reference tonnage (8 000), the protocol includes a provision to increase the financial contribution by EUR 50 for each additional tonne caught.

Annual average turnover: the average turnover of EU tuna vessels from their activities in the Cabo Verde EEZ is estimated at EUR 7 920 000¹² (EU, 2018). Figure 6 illustrates the main income sources for the EU fleet fishing in Cabo Verde. In addition, the estimations of the yearly average for relevant variables at vessel level, based on data available for the period 2016-2020 (STECF AERDB, 2020) are:

- gross value of landings: EUR 3 051 840
- income from leasing the quota: EUR 3 482
- investments: EUR 146 266
- operating subsidies: EUR 8 414
- value of the quota and other fishing rights: EUR 21 102

Figure 6. Main income sources for the EU Fleet in Cabo Verde (2016-2020)

Source: own elaboration with data from STECF AERDB, 2020

¹² The figure has been calculated for the previous protocol, considering the period 2015-2017 “On the basis of catches obtained as a result of fishing opportunities available and average first sale prices of fisheries products” (EU, 2018: 73).

2. **Crew:** the average number of fishers is estimated at 23 crew members per EU vessel for the period 2016-2020 (STECF AERDB, 2020). The FARFISH interviews pointed out that 10% of the crew members are from Cape Verde. This figure is consistent with the one provided by the EU in the Ex-ante and ex-post evaluation of the previous protocol (EU, 2018).

Figure 7. Employment in the EU fleet operating in Cabo Verde (2016-2020)

3. **Operational cost:** these include wages and salaries, fees, energy cost, repair and maintenance, etc.
- The average yearly personnel cost reached EUR 25 035 537 for the period 2016-2020 (STECF AERDB, 2021). Per vessel, the costs are estimated at EUR 651 967 yearly. The insights gathered through the interviews set the average fixed-salary for the crew from Cabo Verde in the EU fleet around EUR 700 per month. The minimum wage in Cape Verde is EUR 117,8 per month (B.O. n77, 2019). It is worth noticing the final salary is linked to the productivity of the catch, therefore varying enormously within the same fishing season. According to one of the interviewees “standard crew member could be earning between 50-100 euros in the low-catch campaigns, and an additional 400-500 euros in high-catch campaigns¹³.
 - Fees average is estimated around EUR 10 083 yearly per vessel (STECF AERDB, 2021). Accordingly, the average fee paid by the EU fleet for the period 2016-2020 is set at EUR 387 197.
 - Energy cost average is set around EUR 497 190 yearly per vessel, being the second highest cost after personnel. The EU fleet operating in Cabo Verde expended in energy more than EUR 19 million per year for the period 2016-2020.
 - Repair and maintenance cost on average are estimated at EUR 252 824 yearly per vessel.

¹³ The fish price sold also influence in the total earnings; for instance, one ton of frigate has more value than one ton of mackerel. Taking Frescomar as the reference processing factory, one ton of frigate is paid around 700€ and mackerel around 600 euros; 90% of the catches are directed to Frescomar

Figure 8. Major cost for the EU Fleet (2016-2020)

Source: STECF AER, 2020.

The economic impact of the SFPA agreement has been calculated for all the entities involved in the protocol. A detailed estimation is provided by the SPFA Assessment (EU, 2018), stating a balance distribution of the gross value added (direct and indirect) between the Cabo Verde (EUR 2.1 million) and the EU (EUR 2.8). Other sources (Oliveira, 2018) focus on the direct value for Cabo Verde (see Table 3 and Table 4) while the methodological approach is slightly different. For instance, Oliveira considers the sectoral development component in the calculus. On the other hand, the SPFA assessment covers in detail indirect impacts upstream and downstream.

Table 3. Estimated direct value for Cabo Verde within the SPFA between 2015-2017

	2015	2016	2017
Fishing rights (access)	30.322.875	30.322.875	27.566.250
Sectoral development	30.322.875	30.322.875	27.566.250
Licences (taxes)	15.064.404	16.174.222	17.526.622
Crew salary	38.107.584	12.305.574	34.931.952
Total (ECV)	113.819.753	89.127.562	107.593.091
Total (€)	1.032.220	808.285	975.750

Source: Oliveira, 2018

In addition, the direct and indirect multiplier effects generated by the presence of the EU fleet in the Cape Verde EEZ in the main sector of the Cape Verdean economy and the EU, and in particular in the fisheries sector, can be summarized in the following table for the period 2015-2017.

Table 4. Increased value resulting from EU fleet activity within the SFPA from 2015-2017

EU vessels		Period 2015-2017			
	Member State	Average sale Price (€/Ton)	Catches (Ton)	Value (€)	Increased value (€)
Pole-and-line tuna	Spain	2.120	769	1.630.295	733.633
	France	2.120	0	0	0
	Portugal	2.120	0,3	707	318
	Total		769	1.631.002	733.951
Tuna seiners	Spain	1.190	3.284	3.906.605	1.757.972
	France	1.190	54	64.208	28.893
	Portugal	1.190	0	0	0
	Total		3.338	3.970.813	1.786.865
Surfase longiners	Spain	1.753	1.002	1.756.644	790.490
	France	1.753	0	0	0
	Portugal	1.753	1.072	1.879.544	845.795
	Total		2.074	3.636.188	1.636.285
TOTAL			6.181	9.238.003	4.157.101

3.1.3 Human dimension at port

The main activity at port is focused on the canning industry. Industrial catches, mainly tuna species, are basically processed and exported (80%) while catches from the artisanal fleet are directed almost exclusively to the domestic market (20%). The national and the industrial fishing fleet provide raw material to feed two processing plants in São Vicente and São Nicolau.

Oliveira (2018) describes the companies currently operating in the country: Sociedad Ultramarina de Conservas Lda. (SUCLA) and FRESCOMAR (company of UBAGO GROUP MARE S: L.). SUCLA, is a company with national capital located in the municipality of Tarrafal de San Nicolau; essentially is processing tuna to supply the domestic market. The company has a processing capacity of approximately 750 tonnes/year, employing an average of 150 workers, with a high component of women labour. In 2013 and 2014, SUCLA managed to export 20,844 and 35,700 tuna cans to the US and mackerel, respectively.

FRESCOMAR is a company with foreign capital, located in the city of Mindelo, with more than 1.700 workers, where local labour is the 99%, as same as SUCLA, the female labour percentage is also high (around 70%).

Frescomar processing plant at Mindelo, Cabo Verde

Source: <https://www.alimarket.es/>

With a daily production capacity of around 950 tonnes, their products are destined to the international market, essentially Spain, North America, ECOWAS and PALOP markets. Currently, FRESCOMAR imports more than 80% of its raw material needs.

In addition to these two processing plants, there is a sizable freezing complex located in Porto Mindelo. The 'Complejo de Pesca Cova da Inglesa' storages, freezes and processes a diversity of fishing products. The facility occupies an area of 7,192.80 m², managed by the EU company ATUNLO CV.

Infrastructures play a crucial role in the performance of the fishing sector. Although public administration representatives remark a notable improvement in the port facilities, information gathered in the FarFish interviews point out to the need for further enhancement. The respondents consider that port infrastructures are insufficient to keep an adequate and competitive daily-processing activity, lacking enough space and loading docks to assure the number of landings of raw material and other goods. As a result, the processing industry has to face delays and pay the corresponding charge to the port authority in respect of failure to load or discharge the ship within the time agreed¹⁴. In addition, just a few services are currently available at the fishing port: fuel oil provision, water and ice supply.

The main port is Porto Grande located in Mindelo (Island of São Vicente), followed by the port in Praia (Island of Santiago) and the fishing port in Tarrafal (Island of São Nicolau). Basically, around the 80% of captures are landed into these three ports¹⁵, although in the case of Frescomar, all the processed

¹⁴ FarFish interviews, 2021

¹⁵ FarFish interviews, 2021

catches come from purchases in the port of Mindelo, 85% directly in Porto Grande and the remaining 15% in 'Complejo Cova da Inglesa'.

French purse seiners are frequently using the port of Dakar (Senegal) as their operational base, although landings are variable to circumstances (e.g. current location, prices, transshipment opportunities and costs). Nevertheless, Spanish and Portuguese longliners also Spanish purse seiners, generally use the port of Porto Grande (Mindelo) for landing and transshipment their catches to the EU. In fact, along 2020 the port of Porto Grande was the only one of the main ports in Cape Verde registering the movement of fishery products, which suffered a considerable decrease compared to 2019 due to the pandemic (Table 5).

Table 5 Movement of goods (tonnes) by type of cargo in Porto Grande during 2020

Goods	2020	2019	Variation (number)	Variation (%)
Conventional load	194.122	216.500	-22.378	↓ -10,3
Liquid bulk	356.404	423.789	-67.385	↓ -15,9
Containerized cargo	189.643	220.072	-30.429	↓ -13,8
Big bags	22.213	34.482	-12.269	↓ -35,6
Solid bulk	31.623	27.814	3.809	↑ 13,7
Fish	28.888	45.901	-17.013	↓ -37,1
Total	822.893	968.558	-145.665	↓ -15,0

Source: Boletín estadístico 2020. ENAPOR

The institutional design of the SPFA introduced a financial incentive to increase the rate of landings and processing in Cabo Verde. The protocol sets a fee reduction of €10 per ton of tuna landed in ports of Cabo Verde. In addition, if the catches were sold into a Cabo Verdean processing plant it will be granted a supplementary reduction of €10 euros per ton.

Recent analysis (EU, 2018: iv) show that Cabo Verde is emerging as a processing and transshipment hub for the EU fisheries activities in the region. Figures show an increase of the 172% in the transshipment from EU fleet between 2013 and 2017.

Table 6. Transshipment from EU fleet (ton.) 2013-2017

Transshipment from EU fleet (Ton.) along the period 2013-2017.

Fleet nationality	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Spanish	5.651	4.865	7.198	14.911	16.931
Dutch				1.474	
Portuguese	845	501	489	463	728
Total	6.496 €	5.366 €	7.687 €	16.848 €	17.659 €

Transshipment from EU fleet (Ton.) along the period 2013-2017.

Fleet nationality	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Spanish	5.651	4.865	7.198	14.911	16.931
Dutch				1474	
Portuguese	845	501	489	463	728
Total	6.496 €	5.366 €	7.687 €	16.848 €	17.659 €

Source: Boletín estadístico 2020. ENAPOR

Transshipment from EU fleet (Ton.) along the period 2013-2017.

Fleet nationality	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Spanish	5.651	4.865	7.198	14.911	16.931
Dutch				1474	
Portuguese	845	501	489	463	728
Total	6.496 €	5.366 €	7.687 €	16.848 €	17.659 €

3.1.4 Human dimension at international level

The EU has initiated an Economic Partnership Agreement (EPA) with 16 West African states, including Cabo Verde, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and the West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU). This EPA would offer broader trade and development prospects because it could in the future extend to areas beyond trade in goods, including services and investment, which are highly relevant to Cape Verde economy (EU, 2018).

Based on the Ex-post and Ex-ante SPPA evaluation for Cabo Verde (EU, 2018), both the EU and Cabo Verde collaborates in fisheries for more than 35 years. Under the Cotonou Agreement (acting the EU as a partner), Cabo Verde is a beneficiary of the European Development Fund (EDF), being it the main source of technical and financial. The EPA offers broader trade and development prospects because it could in the future extend to areas beyond trade in goods, including services and investment, which

are highly relevant to this small island economy (EU, 2018). Particular, the blue economy aspects already included in the new agreement signed in 2019.

Other relevant aspect of the SFPAs between EU and Cabo Verde provides a clearly defined framework for ensuring future compliance with the external policy fisheries dimension measures of the UE. The added value of the EU role in the Protocol is recognized in the ex-post assessment (EU, 2018), as an instrument to support implementation of an EU fleet management framework coherent with frameworks negotiated under other tuna agreements and regional, national and international level programmes. Finally, in terms of trade relationship Cabo Verde has turned into a processing and a transshipment hub for the EU fisheries activities in the region. Table 7 shows the main tuna trade flow from Cape Verde to Europe. The volumes of exports have increasing from 2014 to 2020 by almost 50% in total. This data is coherent with the catches reported in the previous section. The table also illustrates the importance of the processing industry in Cape Verde. The prepared products of skipjack increased by 70% from 2015 to 2020, and by 50% in the case of prepared products based on yellowfin.

Table 7. Exports of tuna from Cabo Verde to the European Union (in tonnes)

Specie	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Tuna, bigeye	2.458	1.463	1.146	3.011	3.030	6.101	2.722
Frozen	2.458	1.463	1.146	3.011	3.030	6.101	2.722
Tuna, miscellaneous	509	169	438	1.344	1.422	2.290	1.776
Frozen	38	73	261	1.142	677	858	1.348
Prepared/Preserved	471	96	177	201	746	1.432	428
Tuna, skipjack	9.248	9.082	10.611	12.052	13.208	10.178	14.575
Frozen	9.248	8.369	8.541	10.201	10.376	7.835	12.394
Prepared/Preserved		713	2.070	1.851	2.832	2.343	2.182
Tuna, yellowfin	4.520	8.188	10.893	4.698	8.078	7.450	10.848
Frozen	4.519	7.701	9.939	3.461	7.166	6.223	9.747
Prepared/Preserved		484	952	1.237	912	1.227	1.100
TOTAL	16.735	18.901	23.088	21.105	25.738	26.019	29.921

Transshipment from EU fleet (tonnes) along the period 2013-2017.

Fleet nationality	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Spanish	5.651	4.865	7.198	14.911	16.931
Dutch				1.474	
Portuguese	845	501	489	463	728

3.2 Senegal CS

3.2.1 Environmental and fishery dimension

Senegal has 718 km of coastline and its continental shelf spreads over 23,800 km². Located in the western most part of the African continent, Senegal¹⁶ is bordered by Mauritania, Mali, Guinea, and Guinea-Bissau. With such a long coastline, the fisheries sector makes a significant contribution to the economy in Senegal¹⁷.

Figure 9. Map of Senegal and corresponding EEZ

Source: Flanders Marine Institute (2018). Maritime Boundaries Geodatabase: Maritime Boundaries and Exclusive Economic Zones (200NM), version 10

The Senegalese maritime zone is characterized by an extraordinary biological diversity. Exploited resources comprise basically four groups (coastal and deep-sea demersal; coastal and deep-sea pelagics,) with varying bio-ecological characteristics and socio-economic importance.

¹⁶ The World Bank Overview highlights that „Senegal enjoys a dry tropical climate and has a population of 16.7 million people, a quarter of whom live in the Dakar area (0.3% of the territory)”

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/senegal/overview#1>

¹⁷ The country's population is approximately 16 million and the gross national income is around US \$1,400 per capita. <https://data.worldbank.org/country/SN>

The fisheries production has been increasing from the 90s to the present, especially consolidating some notable figures in those periods in which the state of Senegal had signed a fisheries agreement with the EU. The highest fisheries production in recent years was reached in 2017, with near to 536 000 tonnes; on the contrary, the lowest rates are found within those periods, and particularly along 2006, when both parties did not agree on a new fisheries agreement (FarFish D3.8, 2021; Figure 10).

Figure 10. Total fisheries production for Senegal (1996-2018; in tons)

Source. World Bank <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/ER.FSH.PROD.MT?locations=SN>

Diedhiou and Yang (2018) provide figures that illustrate the reliance of the Senegalese fisheries sector: in 2016 fisheries represented a 3.2% of the national GDP, contributed a 14.63% of total value of export earnings, and employed an estimated 600 000 people (more than 53 100 direct and an estimated 540 000 indirect jobs, mainly in artisanal fishing and processing) of which 30% were women.

The production of national and foreign fleet was around 524 851 tonnes, with an estimated commercial value of EUR 272 466 billion in 2018 (DPM, 2018).

According to the FarFish Senegalese case study (2019), the fishing sector is the first export sector with revenues of more than CFA 150 billion per year, representing 15% of the total active labour force.

Senegal has signed bilateral agreements with the EU¹⁸, as well as with other countries in the sub-region. Some of them are reciprocal (e.g. Cape Verde) while others grant access for the Senegalese fleet to other fisheries grounds (e.g. Mauritania). Narrowing the scope to the tuna species, the main ones caught by EU vessels are yellowfin tuna, skipjack tuna and bigeye tuna. For yellowfin and skipjack tuna, there is no quota system in ICCAT. In fact, the 85% of EU catches in the Senegalese EEZ are of tuna species (average 8 800 tonnes per year; EU, 2019).

¹⁸ The EU-Senegal Agreement of 1979 was the first negotiated with a developing country.

In the ICCAT database there is useful information about the catches and fishing effort of major tuna (Bluefin tuna, albacore, yellowfin tuna, skipjack tuna, swordfish among others), small tunas and major sharks (e.g. blue shark). Particularly to the nominal catch information, it is available by specie, region, gear, flag and where possible, separated between EEZ and High Seas¹⁹. However, the level of disaggregation of data does not allow to disentangle the fishing operations developed in Senegal EEZ because the information is aggregated including all the North West Atlantic.

Table 8. Access to tuna under quotas from Senegal and the EU

Species	Total Allowable Catches (tonnes)	EU quota (tonnes)	Senegal quota (tonnes)
Big eye tuna	65.000	16.989	0
North Atlantic Swordfish	13.200	6.718	250*
South Atlantic Swordfish	14.000	4.824	417
Blue marlin	1.670	403	150

(*) The transfer of 125 tonnes from Senegal to Canada and 25 tonnes to Mauritania (provided that Mauritania submits a development plan) is authorised.

Source: *Compendium of management recommendations and related resolutions adopted by ICCAT for the conservation of tunas and tuna-like species in the Atlantic 2020.*

Source: https://www.iccat.int/Documents/Recs/COMPENDIUM_ACTIVE_ENG.pdf

3.2.2 Human dimension at sea

EU vessels from Spain and France have access to Senegalese waters. The current SFPa Protocol 2019-2024 (Council Decision 2019/1925) provides access for a maximum of 45 EU fishing vessels. The agreement includes an amount equivalent to a reference tonnage of 1.750 for deep demersal species (namely, black hake) and 10.000 tonnes per year for highly migratory species²⁰.

All the vessels that will be fishing through this SFPa are tuna vessels (Table 9) with the exception of two trawlers fishing for black hake. The protocol thus contributes to sustainability of the fish stocks, protection of the local fishermen and food security, strict controls and support to the fight against illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (IUU).

¹⁹ <https://www.iccat.int/en/accesingdb.html>

²⁰ [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22019A1120\(02\)&from=EN](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22019A1120(02)&from=EN)

Table 9: Fishing opportunities by type of vessel by Member State fishing within the Senegal SFPA

Type of vessel	Spain	France	Total
Tuna seiners	16	12	28
Surface longliners	3	2	5
Pole-and-line tuna	8	2	10
Trawlers	2	-	2
Total	29	16	45

Source: https://ec.europa.eu/oceans-and-fisheries/fisheries/international-agreements/sustainable-fisheries-partnership-agreements-sfpas/senegal_es

In 2018 a total of 19 EU vessels, including eight pole-and-line tuna vessels, eight purse seiners and three vessels with black hake as target specie had developed fishing campaigns in waters under Senegalese EEZ. The quantity landed was 7,648 tonnes with a value of 5,790 billion FCFA; if we compare it with figures from 2017 where it was obtained 7,837 tons with a value of 5.946 billion FCFA, we can observe both a decrease of 2% in volume and 3% in value (DPM, 2018). A more complete picture of the EU tuna fleet catches is provided in Tables 10 and 11.

Table 10: Captures from EU pole-and-line tuna fleet within the Senegal EEZ – 2018 (t.)

Pole-and-line tuna	JAN.	FEB.	MAR.	ABR.	MAY.	JUN.	JUL.	AUG.	SEP.	OCT.	NOV.	DEC.	TOTAL
1	89,64	28,54	70,51	527,68	273,89	327,47	60,78	11,00	8,00	3,50	123,43		1.524,44
2	69,48			30,21	77,88	82,57	44,71		32,44	273,61	42,04	85,99	738,93
3	11,00		2,08	4,13	5,42	9,94				35,39	9,15	70,59	147,70
4	4,65	10,84	42,27	261,30	65,69	24,34				52,19	29,64		490,92
5	41,49	61,92		10,00	100,84	55,80	3,00	4,48	57,07	213,57	43,48	11,06	602,71
6	1,85	9,75	72,49	201,37	85,26	124,97			16,53	212,98	65,67	91,42	882,29
7	36,16	0,78	33,10	223,60	188,24	100,01		7,00	2,00	2,00	7,82	47,77	648,48
8	1,68	2,00	43,99	85,06	100,74	59,59			4,10				297,16
TOTAL	255,95	113,83	264,44	1343,35	897,96	784,69	108,49	22,48	120,14	793,24	321,23	306,83	5.332,63

Source: Direction des Peches Maritimes - Ministere des Peches et de l'Economie Maritime, 2018

Table 11: Captures by specie from EU pole-and-line tuna within the Senegal EEZ – 2018

Species	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC	TOTAL
Sardinella*	7	5	5	3	12	7		10	2			5	56
White tuna					4							6	10
Bigeye tuna	15	1	2	18	17	12		5	4	5	1	1	81
Skipjack tuna	158	83	257	1.319	859	762	93	5	114	775	300	165	4.890
Albacore	76	25		3	4	3	15	3		14	21	130	294
TOTAL	256	114	264	1.343	896	784	108	23	120	794	322	307	5.331

(*) Sardinella is including two different species

Source: Direction des Peches Maritimes - Ministere des Peches et de l'Economie Maritime, 2018

The fleet consists of seven Spanish pole-and-line vessels represented by shipowners' group ANABAC and French one represented by ORTHONGEL. In addition to the EU vessels, 16 tuna vessels flying the Senegalese flag²¹ are also based in Dakar (DITP, 2019). Six out of the 16 tuna vessels are owned or controlled by Spanish capital, including five bait boats and one purse seiner. Thus, overall, there are 13 pole-and-line vessels and one purse seiner of European flag or capital (FarFish, 2020).

According to tuna shipowners, there would be a stagnation in European fisheries activities within SFPAs. Tuna-related activity carried out by pole and line vessels seems to be increasing in Dakar, mostly due to economic related activities. On the one hand, the operation of the European pole-and-lines vessels in the Atlantic Ocean is relatively stable, while the national Senegalese fleet is growing, to a large degree through foreign investments, including from Spanish operators (FarFish, 2020).

Regarding the EU tuna seiner fleet the fishing activity within Senegal EEZ does appear as a more seasonal activity, focusing almost exclusively during the summer season and more specifically in the June (Table 12). The catch composition both the EU tuna seiners and pole-and-line vessels is rather similar, after observing significant differences until 2015, since the latter also focuses on Skipjack tuna. Tuna seiner fleet have left yellowfin tunas found on free schools since the decrease in number of large Yellowfin groups (Pascual-Alayon et al., 2018); therefore, no evidence appeared in the catches of the last years (Table 13).

Table 12: Captures from EU tuna seiners within the Senegal EEZ – 2018 (t.)

Tuna seiners	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC	TOTAL
1						524							524
2					13		2		7				22
3						24				52			76
4						1				19			20
5							2						2
6						21	3						24
7						164	20						184
8						100	2						102
TOTAL	0	0	0	0	13	834	29	0	7	71	0	0	954

Source: Direction des Peches Maritimes - Ministere des Peches et de l'Economie Maritime, 2018

²¹ The other ten Senegalese flagged vessels have beneficial ownership from South Korea. The whole pole-and-line fleet is active in Senegal, while less than half of seiners are regularly present in Senegalese waters (10 out of 25 vessels active in West Africa between 2014 and 2019 (DG MARE, 2020; FarFish, 2020)

Table 13: Captures by specie from EU tuna seiners within the Senegal EEZ - 2018 (t.)

Species	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC	TOTAL
Bigeye tuna						11			2	5			18
Frigate tuna						14	1			2			
Chub mackerel						28							28
Skipjack tuna					13	740	26		5	61			845
Albacore						41	2			3			46
TOTAL					13	834	29		7	71			954

Source: Direction des Peches Maritimes - Ministere des Peches et de l'Economie Maritime, 2018

The facts and figures of the agreement have been used for assessing the economic impact of the SFPA. Following the method described in section 2.1, socioeconomic variables are calculated.

1. Financial contribution (Protocol, 2019, article 4):

- the EU's contribution includes a public contribution to compensate for the access to the resources and to support the Senegalese fisheries policy, as well as a private contribution by vessels owners operating under the agreement.
- Financial compensation for access to resources: EUR 800 000 per year, including an amount equivalent to a reference tonnage of 10 000 tonnes per year for highly migratory species.
- Support for the implementation of the sectoral fisheries policy: EUR 900 000 per year
- Fishing licences fees for the fishing authorizations: estimated at EUR 1 350 750 per year.

An anticipated annual flat-rate fee per vessel is used:

- For tuna seiners:
 - First three years: EUR 18 500 per year, corresponding to a tonnage of 231.25 tonnes per year, on the basis of a fee of EUR 80 per tonne
 - Third and four years: EUR 18 500 per year, corresponding to a tonnage of 217.64 tonnes per year, on the basis of a fee of EUR 85 per tonne
- For pole-and-line vessels, EUR 13 000 per year, corresponding to a tonnage of 173.33 tonnes per vessel.
- For longliners, EUR 3 525 per year, corresponding to a tonnage of 47 tonnes per vessel.
- For trawlers, EUR 500 per vessel and per quarter, for a fee of EUR 95 per tonne.

2. Annual average turnover: the average turnover of EU tuna vessels from their activities in the Senegalese EEZ is estimated at EUR 4 752 000 (EU, 2019).

Figure 6 illustrates the main income sources for the EU fleet fishing in Senegal. The data include all vessels. In addition, the estimations of the yearly average for relevant variables at vessel level, based on data available for the period 2016-2020 (STECF AERDB, 2020) are:

- gross value of landings: EUR 4 715 341
- income from leasing the quota: EUR 4 555
- investments: EUR 369 053
- operating subsidies: EUR 1 824
- value of the quota and other fishing rights: EUR 1 193 299

Figure 11. Main income sources for the EU Fleet in Senegal (2016-2020)

3. **Crew:** the average number of fishers is estimated at 25 crew members per EU vessel for the period 2016-2020 (STECF AERDB, 2020). In addition, there were 34 equivalent full-time indirect jobs upstream (including 7 from the EU), and 126 equivalent full-time indirect jobs downstream, including 38 in the EU (just only 16 from Senegal) (FarFish, 2020).

Figure 12. Employment of the EU fleet operating in Cabo Verde (2016-2020)

Another relevant economic sector related to the EU fishing activity is the one dedicated to the capture of bait. Although most of the bait fleet belongs to the national company (Société d'exploitation des ressources thonières - SERT²² / Dakar Thon / Sénégalaise de la pêche thonière) it is linked to European ownership interests. In addition, one pole-and-line vessel belongs to the company TUNASEN Sénégalaise de Thon-TUNASEN, which relies on Spanish investment and it is owned by SOPERKA, a Spanish fishing operator, based in Dakar (FarFish, 2020).

The Economic performance of the EU vessel provided by the prospective and retrospective analysis of the last SFPA, had shown the turnover of European bait boats²³ was €7.838 million per year on average between 2015 and 2018 in Senegalese waters (European Commission, 2019).

4. **Operational cost:** these include wages and salaries, fees, energy cost, repair and maintenance, etc.
 - The average yearly personnel cost reached EUR 79 831 294 for the period 2016-2020 (STECF AERDB, 2021). Per vessel, the costs is estimated at EUR 971 184 yearly.

²² The SERT group is large and generates an annual turnover of around 5 to 6 million euros, with annual catches around 3,500 to 4,000 tons (FarFish, 2020)

²³ Some of the mentioned charges have been described as follows (FarFish, 2020):

- The handling and transport costs in the port are €600 per shipment and per container. A shipment consists of 2 to 15 containers, which is serviced on an irregular basis timewise (approx. once every week).
- The monthly costs of storing fish in the only cold warehouse in the port of Dakar (Socofroid, owned by the French group Bolloré) are around €914 for 300 tons (€3.04 per ton) per month, or around €11,000 per year

- Fees average is estimated around EUR 7 744 yearly per vessel (STECF AERDB, 2021). Accordingly, the average fee paid by the EU fleet for the period 2016-2020 is set at EUR 636 557.
- Energy cost average is set around EUR 823 780 yearly per vessel, being the second highest cost after personnel. The EU fleet operating in Cabo Verde expended in energy more than EUR 67.7 million per year for the period 2016-2020.
- Repair and maintenance cost on average are estimated at EUR 633 151 yearly per vessel

3.2.3 Human dimension at port

The Autonomous Port of Dakar (PAD)²⁴ is the leading port of the West African coast.

The port terminal deals with the local market, but also with goods in transit toward the subregion. Dakar Terminal employs over 150 permanent employees and is an integral part of the Emerging Senegal Plan, launched by the authorities, which is aimed in particular at making the Port of Dakar²⁵.

The pole-and-line vessels from the EU are all based in Dakar, which is also their landing port. National tuna fleet (some of them owned by holdings), is also based in Dakar. In terms of further operations and economic activities, the pole-and-line vessels generally store their catches frozen in brine on board for subsequent processing in canneries. A remarkable difference is found for those products exported from the port of Dakar, where tuna products are mainly processed into loins or frozen which is only a minor part of the whole product transformation (FarFish, 2019). These products would then be shipped mainly to Europe and Thailand, according to interests from Princes Group (UK) and Thai Union Group PCL (Thailand). A minor portion of the catch intermittently supplies the two canneries based in Dakar (SCASA and CONDAK). In addition, the Senegalese bait boats linked to European investments only supply these canneries sporadically (collected from interviews). They mostly supply Spanish operators based in Spain (Pereira Armadora and FRINSA in particular) (FarFish, 2020).

3.2.4 Human dimension at international level

The export trade flow of Senegal has been increasing year by year to the different destinations at worldwide level. The increase in exports can be explained by certain factors (DPM, 2018):

- The exceptional landings made by Chinese fishing fleet at the port of Dakar;
- The increase in onshore processing units (132 against 130 in 2017) and fishing (105 against 102 in 2017), for a total of 237 units against 232 in 2017 (variation of 2.1%);
- The evolution of potential markets towards the African continent were constantly increasing.

²⁴ The Container Terminal in the North Zone of the Port of Dakar covers an area of 24 ha; it has a quay line of about 700 m with three berths between 12 to 13 m. Modern equipment is used for handling. It is comprised of four docks (including two Panamax posts), four 100-ton Gottwald cranes on wheels, ten gantry cranes, 15 reach-stackers, and 400 refrigerated outlets.

²⁵ <https://www.portdakar.sn/en/nous-decouvrir/presentation/infrastructure>

- Neighbouring countries as Republic of Côte d'Ivoire, among other countries in the sub-region such as Burkina Faso, Mali and Cameroon had experienced strong growth in 2018.

In the case of European trade flow, the main tuna species are represented in the following table:

Table 14. Exports of tuna from Senegal to the European Union (t.)

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Swordfish	2.873	2.806	440	2.184	2.108	1.926	1.182
Live/Fresh	4	6	5	4	6	6	7
Frozen	2.869	2.800	435	2.179	2.101	1.920	1.175
Tuna, albacore	-	1.174	1.739	957	929	936	587
Frozen		1.174	1.739	957	929	936	587
Tuna, bigeye	344	780	813	999	1.046	1.984	1.035
Frozen	344	780	813	999	1.046	1.984	1.035
Tuna, miscellaneous	2.968	248	175	296	449	295	155
Frozen	104	560	156	163	225	221	71
Prepared/Preserved	2.864	247	18	133	225	74	84
Tuna, skipjack	4.952	6.126	4.837	7.553	3.697	4.595	4.316
Frozen	4.952	4.163	4.276	6.898	3.095	3.610	2.808
Prepared/Preserved		1.963	561	656	601	985	1.508
Tuna, yellowfin	5.947	2.729	6.328	4.716	4.198	6.089	4.672
Live/Fresh	85	69	137	47	11	10	8
Frozen	5.862	2.538	6.187	4.657	4.185	6.074	4.654
Prepared/Preserved		121	4	12	1	5	10
TOTAL	17.084	13.862	14.332	16.705	12.426	15.825	11.946

The top export destinations of "Fish commodity" from Senegal in 2020 was France, Spain, Italy and Belgium (summing up more than 90% in value terms). There is an increasing trend regarding the prepared and preserved products, in particular for those made with yellowfin, skipjack and bigeye.

On the other hand, it should be considering those other issues related to international relations between countries when sharing mutual interest, such the constitution of a Fisheries Improvement Project (FIP) for pole-and-line tuna Fishery in Senegal. Jointly led by Dakar Tuna shipowner group (in charge of pole-and-line vessels under European flags), Senegalese shipowner TUNASEN (under Spanish capital), WWF-UK and some manufacturers (Thai Group from Thailand, Princes Group from UK and SENEMER from Senegal), the project aims to improve stocks management, environmental impacts and efficiency of the sector, in order to achieve Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) standards. Therefore, the products would be valued, in order to reach demanding markets in terms of quality (FarFish, 2020).

The EU and Senegal are cooperating under the general framework of the Cotonou Agreement. Actions in supporting the fishing sector are made through the Regional Indicative Programme (RIP) (€1,150 million) and more specifically through the framework of the PESCAO programme, the aim of

which is to improve governance in the fisheries sector and combat illegal fishing with funding of €15 million over the 2018-2024 period.

However, a new roadmap for the development of the fishing sector was approved in 2016 in the sectoral policy on the development of fisheries and aquaculture (LPSDPA in French) for the 2016-2023 period, itself a part of the Plan Sénégal Emergent (PSE). The LPSDPA provides for support to sustainable management of resources, development of aquaculture and promotion of fisheries products through a horizontal programme to strengthen the capacity of sectoral actors. The 2016-2023 LPSDPA also sets a follow-up evaluation framework which includes an annual joint review involving partners, among whom the EU.

On the other hand, Senegal has ratified most of the international instruments relating to international fisheries governance. Senegal is a contracting party or cooperating party to the RFMOs which have competence over the fisheries targeted by Senegal's vessels. In addition, Senegal ratified the FAO Port State Measures Agreement in 2017, a positive development given the importance of the port of Dakar for the landings of fisheries products caught in various zones of the sub-region by vessels flying a range of flags.

4 Conclusion

The methodological approach used in this report provides a more accurate description of the human dimension of the SFPA. Namely, it allows to include variables not considered in the current ex-ante ex-post evaluation: for instance, the interconnection between fishing and processing sector, including the infrastructure and logistic services associated.

While data availability is a recurrent barrier to analyse the human dimension, the method combines quantitative and qualitative sources to develop a comprehensive picture. Furthermore, it relays on current data sets as the STECF Economic Analysis to obtain data specifically linked to the SFPAs.

The analysis of Cabo Verde points out that the tuna fisheries is fundamental for the EU fleet, prompting a development of the processing industry and driving local socioeconomic development while providing prepared high-quality products to the European market. In this report is highlighted and measured the relevance in socio-economic terms of the fisheries sector through quantitative indicators. The fishing sector employs about 6 to 8% of the active population (6,300 FTE), exporting more than 80% of total (\$95.5M in 2019). In this sense, the quantification of the processing seafood products identified the tuna cans and non-fillet frozen fish as the more relevant preservations of catches. Additionally, the main weaknesses (e.g. lack of proper infrastructures) related to the processing sector were identified through the qualitative research. In this case, allocation of resources to improve the infrastructures that support the position of Cabo Verde as a hub may be determinant for on-going and future activities.

In the case of Senegal, the positioning of the EU fleet in the fisheries context is relatively less important due to the plurality of species, actors and trade flows. Nevertheless, the agreement has facilitated the links between EU capital and local fleets through mixed ventures. In addition, the official figures of the European fleet operating there were adjusted according to the information gathered. Particularly, the active fleet is composed by seven Spanish pole-and-line and a French one. In addition to the EU vessels, five bait boats and one purse seiner is operating with Senegal flag but financially controlled by EU operators.

Qualitative information also supports the nuances in what is the current status and what relevant needs to address. In this sense, more research to clarify the trade flows of seafood is required. In particular for those flows that involves other external fleets (e.g. Chinese or Turkish).

This report is somehow a proof of concept on how to address the human dimension of the fisheries agreements. Considering the number of research projects, transfer of knowledge initiatives and even the activities of the Joint Scientific Committees of the SFPA, this could be an approach worth to explore further.

Finally, approaching the human dimension on fisheries agreements would have straight implications, at least on two different levels: (1) as a management tool, in order to support the evidence-based for informed decision-making, by incorporating new variables to be taken into account in the evaluation of the agreements; (2) as a formula of cohesion, by highlighting relevant socioeconomic aspects (usually hidden and difficult to trace), allowing higher social acceptance and stakeholder buy-in.

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ANNEX 1 QUESTIONNAIRES FOR THE INTERVIEWS

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR DECISION-MAKERS

1. How many vessels are fishing into the EEZ? (tacking as reference the last 5 years)
2. What type of vessels (by gear) from EU and national are fishing into the EZZ?
3. How was the evolution of the fishing seasonality? New vessel incorporations, scrapping, changes in target species, other, ...)
4. How many fishers are officially currently working in EEZ? ¿How is the percentage of native/local crew?
5. Could you estimate an average salary on board, according to the different types of work on board (crew, second captain, first captain, ...)
6. What do you think about the state of the infrastructures (ports, roads, loading docks)?
7. What any other support services available in the port? And in nearby areas?
8. Identify the main ports by landed species? What is the percentage of catches landed by port (annual/campaign)
9. What is the end point of these captures? What markets (local, national, international) are these catches targeting?
10. How does the EU fleet contribute to the local economy? Is there any national industry (processing / transformation) which has straight commercial relationship with the catches captured by EU fleet within the EEZ? What is the percentage of the fishing captures within the EEZ used by these processing companies?
11. Are there cooperation or training programs developed or involved by the EU fleet? If yes, how many of them bring the focus on local communities?
12. Are there any other collaboration between the national fleet and the UE? (e.g. co-ownership, investments sharing, ...? And how do these developments contribute / affect the sustainable management within EZZ?

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE INDUSTRY

1. How many workers are currently on board? ¿How is the percentage of native/local crew?
2. What is the salary distribution on board, according to the different types of work on board (crew, second captain, first captain, ...)
3. What are the main associated operating costs on your vessel into a fishing campaign? (Please, indicate all relevant costs (fuel, crew, maintenance, licenses, taxes, ...)
4. Did you get any kind of subsidy? (If yes, please cite the amount and the subsidized concept)
5. What do you think about the state of the infrastructures (ports, roads, loading docks, ...) and your daily activity?
6. What any other support services available in the port (for instance, frozen plants, fuel provision)? And in nearby areas?
7. What is the main ports where you landed the fishes? What is the percentage of catches landed by port (annual/campaign)?
8. What is the end point of these captures? What markets (local, national, international) are these catches targeting?

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE PROCESSING INDUSTRY

1. How many workers are currently at the company? ¿How is the percentage of national workers? ¿and the female and male percentage?
2. What is the salary distribution, according to the different types of work on the processing plant board (average)
3. What are the main associated operating costs for your company? (Please, indicate all relevant costs)
4. Did you get any kind of subsidy? (If yes, please cite the amount and the subsidized concept)
5. What do you think about the state of the infrastructures (ports, roads, loading docks, ...) and your daily activity?
6. What any other support services available in the port (for instance, frozen plants, fuel provision)? And in nearby areas?
7. What are the main ports where do you buy your products? If there are some, what is the percentage of products do you buy by port (annual/campaign)?
8. What is the end point of these captures? What markets (local, national, international) are these products targeting?
9. How does the EU fleet contribute to the local economy? Has your company a straight commercial relationship with the catches captured by EU fleet within the EEZ? What is the percentage of the fishing captures within the EEZ used by your processing company?

10. Is there any other national industry (processing / transformation) which has straight commercial relationship with the catches captured by EU fleet within the EEZ? What is the percentage of the fishing captures within the EEZ used by other processing companies? (average)
11. Are there any cooperation or training programs developed or involved by the EU fleet and/or processing companies? If yes, how many of them bring the focus on local communities?
12. Are there any other collaboration between the national industry and the UE? (e.g. co-ownership, investments sharing, ...? And how do these developments contribute / affect the sustainable management within EZZ?

ANNEX 2 CHARACTERIZATION OF THE EU FISHING FLEET SEGMENTS FOR CABO VERDE AND SENEGAL

CAPE VERDE

Vessels using hooks (+40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Energy costs

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Vessels using hooks (20-40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Vessels using hooks (20-40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota
- Energy costs

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Vessels using hooks (20-40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Purse seiners (+40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Demersal trawlers and/or demersal seiners (20-40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Demersal trawlers and/or demersal seiners (+40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

SENEGAL

Pelagic trawlers (+40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Pelagic trawlers (+40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Demersal trawlers and/or demersal seiners (+40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Purse seiners (+40m)

COSTS

- Repair & maintenance costs
- Personnel costs
- Lease/rental payments for quota

INCOME

- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Investments
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Demersal trawlers and/or demersal seiners (+40m)

COSTS

- Lease/rental payments for quota
- Repair & maintenance costs
- Energy costs

INCOME

- Investments
- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Demersal trawlers and/or demersal seiners (20-40m)

COSTS

- Lease/rental payments for quota
- Repair & maintenance costs
- Energy costs

INCOME

- Investments
- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Demersal trawlers and/or demersal seiners (+40m)

COSTS

- Lease/rental payments for quota
- Repair & maintenance costs
- Energy costs

INCOME

- Investments
- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Vessels using hooks (20-40m)

COSTS

- Lease/rental payments for quota
- Repair & maintenance costs
- Energy costs

INCOME

- Investments
- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Vessels using hooks (20-40m)

COSTS

- Lease/rental payments for quota
- Repair & maintenance costs
- Energy costs

INCOME

- Investments
- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

Purse seiners (+40m)

COSTS

- Lease/rental payments for quota
- Repair & maintenance costs
- Energy costs

INCOME

- Investments
- Value of quota and other fishing rights
- Operating subsidies
- Income from leasing out quota
- Gross value of landings

EMPLOYMENT

- Engaged crew
- FTE national

